

Surveys of other rotation crops in rice soils under upland conditions showed the infestation of ragi, wheat, and sorghum in that order. Some grasses in and around rice fields (*Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus* sp., *Alternanthera sessilis*, *Eragrostis pilosa*, *Eleusine aegyptica*, and *Cynodon dactylon*) were found to be suitable

hosts for this nematode. In rice followed by the fodder grass crop *Pennisetum pedicellatum*, nematode infestation resulted in 12 to 17% yield loss. A preliminary survey of areas in Kerala, Gujarat, Orissa, West Bengal, and Assam confirmed the prevalence of *P. indicus* in association with rice culture. ❧

Some granular insecticides tested against rice brown spot disease

G. G. Mukherjee, Mycology Section, and S. C. Sen, Entomology Section, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

To explore their potential for controlling brown spot disease of rice, monocrotophos 5 G, MIPC 4 G, quinalphos 5 G, and AC 92100 5 G, mixed with 20 ml potato-dextrose-agar, were bioassayed against the disease pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan in vitro.

Colony diameter (mm) of mycelial growth of *H. oryzae* 7 days after inoculation ^a(mean of three replicates).

Treatment	Colony diameter (mm) at insecticide doses of				
	1000 ppm	500 ppm	250 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm
Monocrotophos 5 G	—	—	—	—	—
MIPC 4 G	—	—	—	—	—
Quinalphos 5 G	—	—	—	18.3	20.0
A.C. 92, 100	—	15.0	15.6	24.0	30.0
Check	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0	65.0

^a 8 mm.

The growth of *H. oryzae* was inhibited by all the granular formulations (see table) even at the lowest test dose. It was completely inhibited by monocrotophos and MIPC at the dose of 50 ppm, by quinalphos at 250 ppm, but by AC 92100 5 G only at 1,000 ppm. Granular formulations of the above insecticides may be useful in the control of rice brown spot disease. However, more detailed investigations are needed to prove their potential against *H. oryzae* in the field. ❧

the type of information sought are being modified with experience. The process of station-establishment needs improvement, and states and farmers need to become better prepared to undertake control measures in large areas on short notice.

DPPOS also organizes roving surveys during kharif in Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Assam, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, and West Bengal, chiefly to monitor populations of the tungro vector *Nephotettix virescens*. DPPQS processes the data and issues weekly bulletins. When *N. virescens* counts reach two or three insects per rice hill, state governments are advised to begin control measures. Control alerts are also provided for other pests and diseases. It is planned to extend these roving surveys together areas and other rice seasons.

Following an epidemic in Kerala, DPPQS and the State have also organized a special surveillance program for the brown planthopper. In many cases it now is possible to provide timely warning of upcoming pest problems, although not always possible to institute timely control measures. ❧

Proposed integrated studies of pest control problems

Renuka Sengupta and J. J. Ghosh, Department of Biochemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta - 19, India

A study is planned to evolve an integrated picture of the interactions among the pests, pesticides, and nontarget organisms involved in rice culture.

The first part of the study will investigate the action of different organochlorine, organophosphorous, and carbamate pesticides on such nontarget organisms as goats, sheep, rats, frogs, fish, and invertebrates (e.g. mollusks and earthworms). The second part will emphasize the mode of action of the pesticides in important rice pests (e.g. *Tryporyza* sp. and *Chilo* sp.) and the pests' relative sensitivity to different pesticides. Changes in soil chemistry also will be studied.

Several biochemical parameters of target and nontarget organisms, such as

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice surveillance in India

S. N. Banerjee and K. C. Mathur, Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage, Faridabad - 121 001, India

India is beginning to associate surveillances of rice pests with control measures and research. Among several surveillance programs is a pilot program of the Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine, and Storage (DPPQS) to monitor rice, potatoes, sugarcane, and wheat from Central Surveillance Stations in 12 districts in 9 states. Each

station has a surveillance officer and six field reporters. Each field reporter collects data weekly from 20 fixed fields of the selected block in which he works with sampling equipment, meteorological equipment, and light traps. He also makes a weekly roving survey of a portion of the block. State governments use the surveillance information, along with economic threshold values supplied by the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, to determine need for pest control measures and type of control needed. Sampling methods and

acetylcholinesterase, cholinesterase, and adenosine triphosphatases (both Mg^{++} and $Na^+ - K^+$ ATPases) in brain, blood, and other tissues are study targets. The effect

of pesticides on rice plants, particularly on vegetative growth and on the incidence and varieties of insect infestation, will be investigated. ❧

Seed mats used in screening for gall midge resistance

G. van Vreden, entomologist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia

In Indonesia we have developed and applied three methods for screening rice varieties for gall midge resistance:

(a) open field screening, (b) continuous screening using colonized midges in the greenhouse, (c) testing inside easy-to-assemble screenhouses in the field. For (c), we started sowing 2 or 3 weeks before an expected peak in insect emergence. Midges were collected with mouth aspirators and released on miniplots in the screenhouses. The method was satisfactory but laborious because the seeds had to be individually sown 2–3 cm apart, 20 seeds/row for each variety. We developed a method for preparing seed mats in advance.

Sowing distances are marked with ink on a sheet of paper, which is then covered by a transparent sheet of plastic, followed by paper tissue. The tissue is brushed with a thin starch solution to make it sticky and transparent. A cardboard strip on which varieties are identified by number is glued to the left side. Seeds are placed one by one on the marked spots. A second tissue is placed on top and gently pressed down with a brush. The sheets are picked up with the plastic underneath them and placed in the sun or in an airconditioned room to dry. The mats are sown on wet soil. Labels are placed beside the numbers on the sheets.

The method provides quick and accurate sowing, reduces the chance of sowing errors in sequence of varieties, prevents moving and loss of seeds when wetted carefully, and makes it easy to sow at distant sites with little instruction. ❧

Seed mats are prepared in advance of a test in Indonesia for varietal resistance to gall midge.

A new mite pest of rice in India

Y. S. Rao and P. K. Das, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753006, Orissa, India

Spider mites of the genera *Oligonychus* and *Paratetranychus* have previously been reported causing foliage damage to rice in India. During November 1975 plants were observed to have poorly exerted earheads and necrotic leaf sheaths, which were associated with feeding by mites. All mite stages were present between the stem and leaf sheath. Affected glumes had brownish to black lemmata and paleae and shriveled ovaries. The mite has been identified as *Steneotorsonemus spinki* Smiley: Tarsonemid by R. L. Smiley, USDA, Beltsville, Maryland, USA, who says it has been previously collected from rice in Kenya and Taiwan. Panicle deformation has previously been attributed to *S. nodecossas* in Madagascar by V. H. Hai in 1968.

We are continuing research to determine the nature of damage due to *S. spinki*. ❧

Integrated control of *Chilo suppressalis* in Iran

P. Mostowfi, Plant Pests and Diseases Research Laboratory, Shasavar, Iran

Since 1972, when *C. suppressalis* was first collected in rice fields in Northern Iran, we have used cultural controls (plowing and flooding fields, removing stubble and host plant weeds, growing short-duration varieties) and selective insecticides against the pest. Results have been good.

In studying biological control of the pest, we have found three parasites and a disease of the insect:

1. *Trichogramma evanescens* (egg parasite)
2. *Apanteles* sp. (larval parasite)
3. *Andralus spinidems* (larval parasite)
4. *Beauveria bassiana* (larval disease)

The research is incomplete. ❧